

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

STEROPES

D#-WP0.3

**Improvements in estimation of soil properties
using satellite imagery - Synthesis of
STEROPES results**

Due date of deliverable: M54
Actual submission date: 31.07.2024

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Project title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	D-#WP0.3[Catégorie]
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	Improvements in estimation of soil properties using satellite imagery - Synthesis of STEROPES results
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Final report
DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.14056688
License:	CC BY 4.0
AUTHORS OF THE REPORT:	Emmanuelle Vaudour (INRAE), Johanna Wetterlind (SLU), Fenny van Egmond (WR), Luboš Borůvka (CZU), Fabio Castaldi (CNR), Pim Dik (WR), Mohammad Farzaman (INIAY), Youssef Fouad (Institut Agro), Frank Liebisch (AGS), Artur Lopatka (IUNG), Didier Michot (Institut Agro), Pasquale Nino (CREA), Mehdi Saberioon (EV-ILVO), Michael Simmler (AGS), Adrian Vanderhasselt(EV-ILVO)
WITH THE CONTRIBUTION OF (by alphabetical order):	Mukhtar Abubakar (AgroPT), Chapman Agyeman Prince (CZU), Eric Asamoah (WR), Dominique Arrouays (INRAE), Nicolas Baghdadi (INRAE), Hassan Bazzi (AgroPT), Liliane Bel (AgroPT), Nick Berckvens (EV-

ILVO), Gabriele Buttafuoco (CREA), Bert Callens (EV-ILVO), Nádia Luísa Castanheira (INIAV), Eric Ceschia (INRAE), Aldo Dal Prà (CNR), Lucas de Carvalho Gomes (AU), Maxence Dodin (AgroPT), Asa Gholizadeh (CZU), Panos Ilias (EV-ILVO), Radka Kodešová (CZU), Vahid Khosravi (CZU), Cantekin Kivrak (TAGEM), Muhamed Halil Koparan (ATGEM), Alberto Lazaro (INIA), Florent Levavasseur (INRAE), Lucie Martin (INRAE), Jose Luis Gabriel (INIA), Maria Conceição Gonçalves (INIAV), Silvia Obber (ARPAV), Ayşe Özge Savaş (TAGEM), Ana Marta Paz (INIAV), Paul Quataert (EV-ILVO), Francesca Ragazzi (ARPAV), Anne Richer-de-Forges (INRAE), Jose Antonio Rodriguez (INIA), Greet Ruyschaert (EV-ILVO), Tülay Tunçay (TAGEM), Diego Urbina-Salazar (INRAE), Jonas Volungevičius (LAMMC), Dennis Walvoort (WR), Hayfa Zayani (Institut Agro), Renaldas Žydėlis (LAMMC), Daniel Žížala (CZU)

ABSTRACT

Conventional high-detail soil maps are static and often based on obsolete data. STEROPES intended to overcome these limitations putting the use of satellite time series forward, to test their potential to predict cropland soil organic carbon content over various pedoclimatic conditions and cropping systems across Europe. The overall aim of the STEROPES project was to test the potential to use satellite images to predict soil organic carbon (SOC) content in agricultural soils across Europe. The specific aims were trifold: i) assess robustness of spectral models according to agroecosystems/soil types; ii) assess/account for disturbing/influencing soil surface factors; iii) incorporate 1- and 2- results into spatial models.

The first phase of the project consisted of constructing models from the reflectance image spectra of optical satellite series, notably Sentinel-2 (ESA), based on a number of diversified areas for which soil organic carbon samples were already available. Over the course of the project, several datasets have been collected focusing on small regions of some hundreds of km² and on detailed scales of fields and

farms from a few hectares to more than 450 ha, for which soil organic carbon samples were already available.

The second phase of the project was dedicated to analysing the influence of various factors on SOC prediction performance: soil moisture, texture, green and dry vegetation due to management practices, and salinity. Then, for the sites where satellite information may not enable to derive acceptable predictions, other ancillary data such as gamma-ray layers were considered. Field campaigns were carried out in order to complement or to provide datasets.

Spectral models were constructed from the reflectance image spectra of optical satellite series, using several commonly used algorithms including linear regression (LM), partial least squares regression (PLSR), support vector machine regression (SVM) and random forest (RF).

Encouraging performances could be yielded ($RPIQ \geq 1.7$), but this varies in time and geographical space according to several factors especially soil moisture, texture, dry vegetation due to management practices.

We obtained a number of relevant outcomes: first, a step-forward for digital soil mapping (DSM) of SOC content, a step-forward for the remote sensing of soils; second, enhancement of transnational collaboration and impact on approaches for carbon balance accounting; and finally, opening up of links with stakeholders for an enhanced use of remote sensing.

The results from the project contributes especially to the EJP SOIL expected impact “Supporting harmonized European soil information, including for international reporting.

Table of Contents

List of Tables.....	5
List of Figures.....	6
List of acronyms and abbreviations.....	7
1. Introduction.....	9
1.1 Context.....	9
1.2 Aims.....	10
2. Prediction of soil properties using Earth Observation data.....	11
2.1 Spectral model estimations.....	11
2.2 Digital Soil Mapping (DSM) based on environmental variables.....	12
2.3 Bare soil imagery.....	13
2.4 Hyperspectral imagery.....	14
3. Baselines.....	16
3.1 Sample based models: average and interpolation models.....	18
3.2 Spectral baselines.....	22
3.3 DSM using measured covariates.....	23
DSM on local scale - Results of trial fields – Plassteeg (Netherlands).....	23
DSM on regional scale.....	26
3.4 Comparison with existing SOC maps.....	29
Results of trial fields.....	30
Alternative from literature.....	31
3.5 Overview of STEROPES results for different SOC calculation methods at field scale.....	32
4. Factors influencing predictions using bare soil imagery.....	33
4.1 Soil Moisture.....	33
4.2 Soil texture.....	37
4.3 Dry and green vegetation.....	39
4.4 Salinity.....	41
5. Sentinel-2 as a basis for soil sampling strategy.....	44
6. Conclusion and recommendations.....	45
6.1 Conclusion.....	45
6.2 Recommendations.....	46
6.4 Suitability for various purposes of EO for soil estimates for different uses.....	47
List of references.....	48

List of Tables

Table 1. Compared SOC prediction performances between Sentinel-2 and EnMAP in the Czech Republic.....	17
Table 2. EU wide available soil maps used as additional baselines.....	18
Table 3. Overview of field locations, sampling years and number of samples.....	19
Table 4. Characteristics of the mean measured SOC-content per field (mass %) axis and the mean SOC-content based on the available maps.....	32
Table 5. Description of models with used datasets constructed in the framework of WP6.....	33

Table 6. Description of models constructed in the framework of WP6..... 34
 Table 7. Description of soil datasets constructed in the framework of WP5..... 43

List of Figures

Figure 1. STEROPES context and motivation (Vaudour and Wetterlind, 2021) 10
 Figure 2. Overall STEROPES approach (Vaudour and Wetterlind, 2021) 11
 Figure 3. Overall STEROPES structuring and abbreviated goals..... 12
 Figure 4. Plot of performance indicators versus range (top) or standard deviation (down) of measured SOC contents for all models (Vaudour et al., 2022) 13
 Figure 5. General flowchart of the temporal mosaicking approach (from Castaldi et al., 2023)..... 15
 Figure 6. EnMAP averaged raw reflectance (blue line) and variation (purple) for the two Czech sites 16
 Figure 7. Scatterplot of the measured Soil Organic Carbon content (meas, %) against the predicted SOC (pred) for the Plassteeg field in the Netherlands 20
 Figure 8. Maps of the predicted Soil Organic Carbon content (mass, %) using the different methods for the Plassteeg field in the Netherlands 21
 Figure 9. Coefficient of determination and Root Mean Square Error for the models based on sample data only, site Plassteeg, the Netherlands 22
 Figure 10. Mean (mass %), Root Mean Square Error (mass %) and Ratio of Performance to Deviation (-) (no unit) for the models based on sample data for the fields 23
 Figure 11. Correlation matrix for Plassteeg field (Netherlands) of the SOC with the available baselines 25
 Figure 12. Coefficient of determination and Root Mean Square Error for the models based on baselines data, site Plassteeg, the Netherlands..... 26
 Figure 13. Scatterplots for the linear models of the measured Soil Organic Carbon content (meas, %) against the predicted SOC (pred). 27
 Figure 14. Flowchart of the temporal mosaicking of bare soil (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2024)..... 28
 Figure 15. Flowchart of the modeling approach for SOC (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2024) 28
 Figure 16. Relative importance of the environmental covariates for the best SOC prediction model for La Beauce (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2023)..... 29
 Figure 17. SOC map (left) and uncertainty map (right) for La Beauce best model (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2023)..... 30
 Figure 18. Scatterplot of the measured SOC-content (%) on the x-axis and the SOC-content of the available SOC-maps on the y-axis for the Dutch Plassteeg field 31
 Figure 19. Scatterplot of the mean measured SOC-content (%) on the x-axis and the mean SOC-content of the available SOC-maps on the y-axis 32
 Figure 20. Estimated versus observed soil moisture (SM). Left panel: RS SM derived from VH polarization; Right panel: RS SM derived from VH polarization 36
 Figure 21. Scatterplots of measured vs. predicted SOC content for the calibration dataset using Sentinel-2 bands and partial least squares (PLS), random forest (RF) and deep neural network (DNN) algorithms (Zayani et al., 2023) 37
 Figure 22. Cross-validation RMSE values (%) for spectral models of SOC content from temporal mosaics of bare soil..... 38
 Figure 23. The relationship between SOC or SOM and clay content in a European and a national data set. And the correlation between SOC and clay content at 34 fields/farms in 10 European countries39

Figure 24. A) Performance of site-specific PLSR models for predicting SOC using satellite data. B) Performance of site-specific PLSR models for predicting clay using satellite data. RPD and ccc were determined in leave-one-out cross-validation 40

Figure 25. Reference maps prepared after classification of the reference image for a) Nová Ves nad Popelkou, b) Jičín, c) Klučov and d) Přestavlky sites (Khosravi et al., 2024) 41

Figure 26. Scatter diagrams comparing the observed and estimated bare soil fractions from Landsat8 (a, b, c) and Sentinel-2 (d,e, f) using a, d) Index-based, b, e) unmixing-based, and c, f) integrated approaches (Khosravi et al., 2024) 42

Figure 27. Sampling locations over the Sminja Plain (left) and the Lezirias estuarine area, Portugal (right)..... 43

Figure 28. Figure 27. Sampling locations over the Sminja Plain (left) and the Lezirias estuarine area, Portugal (right) 44

List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
ESA	European Space Agency
JRC	Joint Research Centre
ISRIC	International Soil Research and Information Centre
DSM	digital soil mapping
SOC	soil organic carbon
SOM	soil organic matter
TOC	total organic carbon
EOM	exogenous organic matter
LUCAS	Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey
SoilGrids	system for digital soil mapping based on a global compilation of soil profile data
WoSIS	World Soil Information Service
GSOC	Global Soil Organic Carbon map
EO	Earth observation
RS	remote sensing
GPS	global positioning system
UAV	unmanned aerial vehicle
S2	Sentinel-2
EnMAP	Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program
MSI	multi-spectral instrument
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
NIR	near-infrared spectral range
Vis-NIR	visible and near-infrared spectral range
SWIR	short-wave infrared spectral range
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NBR2	Normalized Burn Ratio 2
Scorpan	general model for DSM (letters standing for potential covariate types: Soil, Climate, Organisms, Relief, Parent material, Age and position)
SSPFe	soil spatial prediction function
cLHS	conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling
lm	linear models
PLSR or pls	partial least squares regression

SVM	Support Vector Machine
RF	Random Forest
QRF	Quartile Random Forest
LASSO	least absolute shrinkage and selection operator
DNN	Deep Neural Network
cs	Cloud Score
GEE	Google Earth Engine
IDW	Inverse Distance Weighting
R90	90 th percentile reflectance value
LOO	Leave-One-Out method
RMSE	root mean square error
RPD	ratio of performance to deviation
RPIQ	ratio of performance to interquartile distance
ccc	Lin's concordance correlation coefficient
R ²	index of determination
ECe	electrical conductivity of saturated paste extract
SM	soil moisture
GWC	Gravimetric water content

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

STEROPES, named after a cyclop from the Ancient Greek mythology, stands for “stimulating novel technologies from earth remote sensing to predict European soil carbon”. The overall context of this project (36 months duration plus 6 months-extension, started on 1st February 2021) stems from the need to spatially estimate and monitor soil properties, and especially soil organic carbon (SOC) content, for decision support and land management, notably regarding carbon balance assessment and the feasibility of carbon credits, and more generally in relation to soil health and ecosystem services assessment.

Conventional high-detail soil maps are static and often based on obsolete data in relation to the time of use. In the last decades, for the purpose of providing maps of for example SOC, Digital Soil Mapping (DSM) has been carried out, starting from a number of soil sample locations with standard chemical analyses of SOC in the lab, to construct spatial, geostatistical models and maps (McBratney et al., 2003; Grunwald, 2010; Grunwald et al., 2015; Wadoux et al., 2019, 2020, 2021). Morphometric data (such as elevation and slope) are often incorporated into this modelling, in conjunction with covariates derived from earth observation such as the vegetation index NDVI (Grunwald et al., 2015; Richer-de-Forges et al., 2023). However, collecting soil samples is time-consuming and labour extensive. STEROPES intended to overcome these limitations pushing the use of satellite time series forward, to test their potential to predict cropland SOC content over various pedoclimatic conditions and cropping systems across Europe. The main aim of STEROPES is to elaborate maps from satellite time series, such as those made available by the European Space Agency through the Copernicus data portal (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. STEROPES context and motivation (Vaudour and Wetterlind, 2021)

The STEROPES consortium was composed of 19 public institutes from 14 countries spread over Europe, hence with highly diverse agropedoclimatic contexts. The first phase of the project consisted of constructing reflectance image spectra of optical satellite series, notably Sentinel-2 (ESA), based on a number of diversified areas for which SOC samples were already available. Over the course of the project, several datasets have been collected focusing on small regions of some hundreds of km² or on

detailed scales of farms or catchments of some km², for which SOC samples were already available with an areal density higher than 1-3 samples/km².

The second phase of the project was dedicated to analysing the influence of various factors on SOC prediction performance: soil moisture, texture, green and dry vegetation due to management practices, salinity. Then, for the sites where satellite information may not enable to derive acceptable predictions, other ancillary data such as gamma-ray data layers were considered.

The third phase of the project included field campaigns that were carried out in order to complement or to provide datasets; the processing of the data and the launch of an additional work package dedicated to emerging research gaps.

This final report compiles the overall results of the work packages and their joint analysis in WP6 of STEROPES. The expected outcome of this task is a report or publication and advice on which methods to apply in which location to obtain as accurate estimates as possible of SOC.

1.2 Aims

Remote-sensing-based soil studies have given rise to quantitative approaches aimed to relate soil reflectance to a target property, according to what can be named « spectral model ». According to the type of measurements performed, either on a sieved soil sample in the lab, under controlled light, or over a soil surface condition in the field under natural light, or even from spatial imagery, we can distinguish different categories of spectral models, either lab, field or image-derived (Fig. 2).

Another approach for spatially characterizing a target property can consist of relating it to the geographical coordinates in order to analyse the spatial structure by means of semi-variograms in geostatistical modelling, here referred to as spatial models.

Figure 2. Overall STEROPES approach (Vaudour and Wetterlind, 2021)

The overall aim of STEROPES was to test the potential to use satellite images to predict SOC content in agricultural soils across Europe, primarily from spectral models (WP1 and WP2 to WP5, WP7) and also from spatial models (WP6) or even from mixed spectral-spatial models (WP6). The specific scientific aims were trifold: i) assess robustness of spectral models according to agroecosystems/soil types; ii) assess/account for disturbing/influencing soil surface factors; iii) incorporate 1- and 2- results into spatial models.

Fig. 3 recalls the overall WP structure and abbreviated goals.

Figure 3. Overall STEROPES structuring and abbreviated goals

2. Prediction of soil properties using Earth Observation data

The distinction between spectral models and spatial models marks a historical dichotomy between so-called « remote sensing-based approaches » and « digital soil mapping approaches ». These approaches have developed separately, and only recently they have started to converge (Gomez et al., 2024). It ought to be mentioned, that two review papers (Vaudour et al., 2022; Richer-de-Forges et al., 2023) have been written and one webinar (Gomez et al., 2024) was given in the framework of the STEROPES project, with the purpose to provide a recap of the state-of-the-art in terms of spectral models from Earth Observation data (Vaudour et al., 2022), and more generally on the contribution of remote sensing to digital soil mapping (Richer-de-Forges et al., 2023; Gomez et al., 2024).

2.1 Spectral model estimations

The overall background for using remote sensing is the fact that in addition to spatial structure, soil properties, and particularly SOC, have spectral features in a number of wavebands of the visible, near-infrared and shortwave infrared that enable to construct spectral models (Fig. 2). Most spectral model estimations from Earth Observation data have relied on multivariate calibration techniques or machine learning algorithms to extract the relevant part of the information for large datasets. Amongst the several multivariate algorithms, Partial Least Square Regression (PLSR) is most widely used and offers the advantage of enabling the understanding of the influence of spectral bands on the SOC prediction. PLSR also has the advantage of being less prone to overfitting when using small sample sets. About one-third of the satellite-derived SOC studies used PLSR, while another third used Random Forest (RF),

and the remaining included MLR, support vector machine (SVM), regression trees such as Cubist, and/or kriging (Vaudour et al., 2022). By fitting a PLSR model, one seeks a few PLSR factors that explain most of the variation in both predictors and responses. Our literature review showed that performances for predicting organic carbon, expressed with RMSE or RPD, vary, with the highest RMSE values observed for the highest spatial national-continental levels (Fig. 4). Performances estimated via RPD (shown in red) vary from 1 to 3, for SOC ranges between 0 and 50 g/kg, with no link between RPD value and SOC range, but the few studies comprising soils very rich in SOC (mostly national-continental-scale) drive the correlation between RMSE and SOC range or standard deviation.

Figure 4. Plot of performance indicators versus range (top) or standard deviation (down) of measured SOC contents for all models (Vaudour et al., 2022)

The magnitude of error is the highest for national to continental scales, where it typically reaches 15 g.kg⁻¹ or even more, exceeding the observed range of values for single fields or some small homogeneous regions. When the intraregional variance of measured SOC contents is small, with a prediction uncertainty range of measured SOC contents of c. 15 g.kg⁻¹ and with very low RPD values, close to 1 or even less, models may not be reliable whatever the acquisition date. In such situations, the spatial structure of the data may be of particular relevance to improve the prediction performance, through mixed models incorporating spectral information into spatial models.

2.2 Digital Soil Mapping (DSM) based on environmental variables

Digital soil Mapping (DSM) emerged in the early 2000s as a new concept for mapping soil properties and/or soil classes using soil information and spatially comprehensive covariates, which builds on the work of H. Jenny in the 1940s (Richer-de-Forges et al., 2023). In their seminal article, McBratney et al. (2003) proposed a framework called the scorpan-SSPF. This framework includes a soil spatial prediction function for soil mapping with spatially auto-correlated errors, often referred to as SCORPAN. As defined by McBratney et al. (2003), SCORPAN is based on seven predictive factors of soil types or soil attributes, namely: (1) s: soil, other or previously measured attributes of the soil at a point; (2) c: climate, climatic properties of the environment at a point; (3) o: organisms, including land cover

and natural vegetation; (4) r: topography, including terrain attributes and classes; (5) p: parent material, including lithology; (6) a: age, the time factor; (7) n: space, spatial or geographic position. The prediction functions can use a wide variety of statistical tools, including regression, classification, geostatistics, machine learning (McBratney et al. 2003, Grunwald 2010, Wadoux et al. 2019, 2021, Arrouays et al. 2020, Chen et al. 2022).

In the early stages of the use of RS for soil mapping, RS was often used to delineate/identify soil types or soil classes (Richer-de-Forges et al., 2023). Owing to the recent increased availability of RS products, and particularly those derived from satellite, airborne, or unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) imagery, almost all DSM approaches rely on RS data to obtain spatially exhaustive environmental covariates, as well as legacy soil, geology, geomorphology, and landforms maps. RS predictions from bare soil can be used as an “s” factor in the SCORPAN model: that is one of the issues dealt with through the WP6 of STEROPES.

2.3 Bare soil imagery

The soil properties mapping from satellite images is based on the interaction between sunlight and soil surface detected by satellite sensors. It follows that there is a need of exposed soil surface without, or with reduced, influence of disturbing factors that can negatively affect the purity of the bare soil spectrum, especially in croplands due to soil management. The main disturbing factors identified are the roughness of the soil surface, presence of vegetation, both green and dry, and soil moisture content (Castaldi 2021; Knadel et al. 2022; Gomez et al., 2022, 2024). A mixed spectrum of soil and vegetation is weaker correlated with soil properties as compared to a pure bare soil spectrum, but also a high soil moisture content lowers the strength of diagnostic spectral features, such as those related to clay minerals. However, also the correlation between reflectance and SOC is generally lower for wet soil as compared to dry soil (Cao et al. 2020).

In this regard, satellite imagery collections offer the possibility to select all the bare soil images in a given period, and from these choose the ones that are least affected by disturbing factors, therefore the ones closest to pure bare and dry soil conditions. However, soil rarely appears as bare over an entire region or farm at a given single date or time period. The short revisit time of the Sentinel-2 mission allows the implementation of temporal mosaicking approaches and thus extending the bare soil area by stitching together bare soil pixels at different dates into one image, and consequently increasing the soil properties mapping area (Vaudour et al. 2021). Obviously, more images across a given time period means increasing the chance of finding cloud-free images with bare soil conditions.

In the framework of the STEROPES project, a pixelwise temporal mosaicking approach was conceived and tested for optimizing the selection of bare soil images using Sentinel-2 imagery collections both at local and regional scale (Castaldi et al. 2023). The mosaicking approach was implemented in the Google Earth Engine (GEE) environment using the Copernicus Sentinel-2 Multi- Spectral Instrument (MSI) level 2A provided by European Space Agency (ESA). For each pixel and acquisition date, three filters and/or masks were applied (Fig. 5):

- I. Cloud filter and cloud mask to remove dates and data affected by clouds and cloud shadows. The combination between Cloud Score (cs)+ and S2_HARMONIZED dataset based on the cs quality band was used.

- II. Green vegetation mask. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was computed and pixels having $NDVI > 0.35$ were discarded because they are affected by green vegetation.
- III. Dry vegetation + soil moisture mask. Normalized Burn Ratio 2 (NBR2) index was computed and pixels having $NBR2 > 0.125$ were discarded because of their dry vegetation and/or by high soil moisture content.

For geographical regions not affected by frequent cloud coverage, and if the chosen time period for satellite time series is not too narrow, a further filter can be applied, leaving only pixels having at least three or five bare soil dates after applying the three filters. This further filter avoids including data derived from a single date that could lead to a spotted composite image, due to remaining disturbing factors (such as related to soil management hence soil roughness, not accounted for in this project), and therefore to a less reliable soil properties map.

Figure 5. General flowchart of the temporal mosaicking approach (from Castaldi et al., 2023).

At this step, for each pixel within the region of interest a certain number of bare soil dates were selected, and two main mosaicking approaches were implemented to return bare soil composite images. The first approach, called Median, involves calculating the median spectrum from each pixel location, with the aim to obtain spectral data representative of the average bare soil conditions not affected by extreme reflectance values. The second, called R90, involves selecting the 90th percentile reflectance values throughout the time series for each band, with the aim to select dry conditions, assuming that higher reflectance corresponds to lower soil moisture content. Using the 90th instead of the highest reflectance, allows to exclude anomalous data that could be detected in the final decile of the distribution mainly due to a cloud mask error.

The final outcome of these two approaches is a composite bare soil map covering most of the region of interest. This layer can be used for extracting spectral data from soil sampling locations or for applying soil properties estimation models and finally obtain soil maps for the entire region.

Median and R90 mosaicking approaches were tested and compared to other mosaicking approaches for the SOC and Clay estimation at the within-farm or within-field scales, for cropland sites of contrasted climates and soil types across the Northern hemisphere (USA, Europe, and Turkey). The results reported in Castaldi et al. (2023) showed how the proposed mosaicking approaches can allow to properly map SOC and clay content, with a satisfying level of accuracy and reduced uncertainty.

2.4 Hyperspectral imagery

ENMAP exercise results WP7

A comparative investigation was conducted to assess the ability of the recently launched and commissioned Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program (EnMAP) hyperspectral sensor,

compared to Sentinel-2, in predicting soil organic carbon (SOC) in agricultural soils. L2A EnMAP products acquired on October 2, 2023, were used for this study. Sentinel-2 Level-2A (L2A) imagery was selected and downloaded to match the acquisition dates of the EnMAP L2A scenes in October 2023. These products covered two agricultural sites in the Czech Republic: Jičín and Přestavlky. The EnMAP images underwent an automated sequence of pre-processing operations, including radiometric correction to top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiance (Level-1B), orthorectification and geometric correction of Level-1B data (Level-1C), and atmospheric correction to bottom-of-atmosphere (BOA) reflectance (Level-2A), along with instrument calibration and quality control (Storch et al., 2023). To reduce noise, bands with wavelengths between 418.2–450 nm and 2400–2445.5 nm were excluded from the raw spectra before further processing (Fig.6).

Figure 6. EnMAP averaged raw reflectance (blue line) and variation (purple) for the two Czech sites

For this study, 118 soil samples were selected from those collected during a sampling campaign in June 2021. Each sample was taken from the topsoil at a depth of 20 cm and composed within an area of 4 m². The sampling followed a stratified random strategy designed by the conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling (cLHS) method. Coordinates of each sampling point were determined using a GeoXM (Trimble Inc., Sunnyvale, California, USA) global positioning system (GPS) with a spatial accuracy of 1 m. A digital ground vertical photograph was taken at each sampling point to serve as ground truth for soil cover type. Samples were air-dried, ground, sieved (≤ 2 mm), and mixed before analysis. The SOC content (%) of each soil sample was determined using the Walkley–Black method, while the pipette method (ISO 11277:2009) was used for clay content analysis (particle size < 0.002 mm). The soil samples were divided into training (75%) and testing (25%) sets using the Kennard–Stone (KS) algorithm (Kennard and Stone, 1969). SOC prediction models were developed using random forest regression with 5-fold cross-validation on the training subset. The performance of these models was then evaluated on the testing dataset. Three random forest parameters were optimized for modeling: i) the number of trees (ntree), ii) the number of variables used for each tree (mtry), and iii) the minimum data per node (nodesize) (Prasad et al., 2006). A grid search within the range of 200 to 2000 determined that 500 was the optimal ntree. The nodesize was set to five, and mtry was set to one-third of the total number of variables. The prediction of SOC using EnMAP data was relatively successful for both sites, separately and combined ($RPD \geq 1.35$, $R^2 \geq 0.56$, $RMSE \leq 0.19\%$) (Table 1). Clay content predictions showed higher statistical accuracy than SOC for both sites, separately and combined ($RPD \geq 1.55$, $R^2 \geq 0.69$, $RMSE \leq 2.45\%$). The most accurate predictions for SOC and clay were obtained for Přestavlky, while the lowest accuracies were found for Jičín. The differences between the

performance of models developed on EnMAP and those developed on the Sentinel-2 imagery were more evident for SOC. Accordingly, the performance of EnMAP for predicting SOC was approximately 28% better compared to Sentinel-2.

Table 1. Compared SOC prediction performances between Sentinel-2 and EnMAP in the Czech Republic

Site	Sentinel-2					EnMAP				
	ME	RMSE	R ²	CCC	RPD	ME	RMSE	R ²	CCC	RPD
Jičín 17 samples	-0.12	0.17	0.45	0.59	0.88	0.08	0.11	0.56	0.63	1.39
	0.41	3.31	0.64	0.68	0.75	-0.28	1.61	0.69	0.69	1.55
Přestavlky 61 samples	0.15	0.17	0.58	0.64	1.53	0.08	0.12	0.64	0.71	2.19
	-0.10	2.27	0.73	0.79	1.66	0.17	1.68	0.76	0.83	2.25
All 78 samples	-0.14	0.23	0.57	0.59	1.26	0.05	0.19	0.61	0.66	1.35
	0.29	2.49	0.61	0.66	1.78	0.26	2.45	0.71	0.75	1.76

SOC prediction results on EnMAP were superior to those constructed on S2 for SOC in the study sites. The difference in the spectral resolution of data types could be the main reason for the dissimilar performances of the models.

3. Baselines

To allow a structured comparison between the different possible approaches of analysing soil property sample and Earth Observation data to derive soil information about the area of interest, in this study several baselines were identified and calculated. These include spectral and spatial models as described in chapter 2. The baselines are:

- Average of sampling data, or **Global Mean**. This is calculated using the values of all sampling locations and therefore equals the result that would be acquired when taking a composite sample at the same sublocations. Yields one value for the entire area of interest.
- **Inversed distance weighting**, using the spatial structure by using points nearby (weights are the inverse of the distance to the pixel) to calculate the soil property value in a pixel. Yields a map of the soil property.
- **Ordinary kriging**, creating a semi-variogram that described the spatial correlation between sampling points and uses the semi-variogram to create a map of the soil property based on the sampling data. Yields a map of the soil property.
- **Voronoi polygons** or declustered Global Mean, calculating Thiessen or Voronoi polygons that draw the border of a polygon surrounding each sample point exactly halfway the distance between two adjacent points, thus creating a mesh of polygons and using the surface of the area of a polygon to assign a weight to its sampling point in calculating the average. Yields a map of the soil property.
- **Spectral baseline**, the spectral model prediction of a soil property following the method described in chapter 2.
- **Digital soil mapping**, using the correlation between available ancillary information about soil forming factors as also included in the Scorpan model (§2.2). This can include generally available data such as Sentinel 2A imagery, the Copernicus Digital Elevation Model (DEM) or

other DEM, and other possibly relevant data layers such as proximal soil sensing layers. This is an example of Digital Soil Mapping as described in chapter 0. Yields a map of the soil property.

As additional baselines existing open EU-wide available soil maps were considered, being:

- **GSOC** map of the Global Soil Partnership produced by member countries and the GSP Secretariat for the globe using nationally available SOC data and gap-filled with SoilGrids. ([“Global Soil Organic Carbon Map v1.5 \(GSOC\) – Datasets – « FAO catalog »](#))
- **JRC-LUCAS** map, produced by the JRC for Europe using the latest LUCAS survey SOC point data. (de Brogniez et al., 2015)
- **SoilGrids**, produced by ISRIC-World Soil Information for the globe using data from WoSIS, a global, harmonised soil database. (Poggio et al., 2021)

Details are provided in Table . All the units were converted to mass %. For the conversion of the GSOC data a density of 1500 kg/m³ was used.

Table 2. EU wide available soil maps used as additional baselines

Product	Unit	Depth	Resolution	Reference
GSOC	ton/ha	0-30cm	750 m	GSOC-reference
JRC_LUCAS	g/kg	0-20cm	650 m	JRC_LUCAS
SOILGRIDS	dg/kg	0-5, 5-15, 15-30cm	318 m	SoilGrids

The baselines were calculated at field scale using existing data of fields across Europe available at STEROPES partners. Because existing data was used, differences in sampling design type are inevitable. Different types of probability (e.g. stratified random sampling) sampling occur in the dataset, also regular grid sampling is used. These different designs, as well as the different sampling densities and soil property value ranges may have an effect on the results. An overview of the locations is provided in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**3 along with the availability of samples at each location.

Table 3. Overview of field locations, sampling years and number of samples

Site	Sampling Year	Number of samples	Site	Sampling Year	Number of samples
Altikon	2022	19	Kluc ov	2021	80
Arenenberg	2022	24	Kocas	2021	120
Bjertrop	2016	175	Lezirias	2022	47
Bjertrop_10	2016	122	Lezirias	2023	16
Bjertrop_21	2016	162	Lyduokiai	2021	112
Brogarden	2016	83	Naizin	2020	83
C_Cartagena	2022	122	Nova Ves nad Popelkou	2021	79
Centro Natta	2023	40	Osinyl	2021	32
Dalaman	2021	82	Pedrazzini	2023	40
Entorp	2016	38	Plassteeg	2021	48
Estrup	2012	38	Plassteeg	2023	48
Faarstrup	2011	84	PO River plain Lombardia	2019	61
Fagna	2024	41	PO River plain Lombardia	2020	89
Field_1	2018	54	PO River plain Lombardia	2021	33
Field_2	2018	53	PO River plain Lombardia	2022	28
Field_3	2018	54	Prestavlky	2021	79
Field_4	2018	18	Reckenholz	2022	21
Field_5	2018	18	Silstrup	2010	53
Gavere2	2021	20	Strickhof	2022	24
Gavere2	2022	20	Tarquinia	2015	50
Gotala	2016	51	Tarquinia	2016	90
Grande Borne	2013	27	Tarquinia	2017	60
Grande Borne	2015	31	Udrnice	2021	76
Grandi	2023	40	Valinava	2021	49
Herrenbuent	2021	35	Vezaiciai	2021	56
Jynde vad	2012	88	Vievininkai	2021	70
			Vindum	1992	285

For the site "Plassteeg" in the Netherlands out of 50 samples taken, 48 samples were used in the analysis because two had unclear location descriptions on the sampling bags.

For all fields the results are calculated and compared according to a standard set of uncertainty metrics, the RMSE, R^2 (general definition), mean, range and if applicable the RPD (Ratio of performance to determination).

3.1 Sample based models: average and interpolation models

This chapter describes the results that are obtained on the trial fields for the baselines to obtain an average and other statistical characteristics without ancillary data layers: global average, Voronoi

polygons (area weighted), Inverse distance weighted and Kriging. For inverse distance weighted the square of the distance was used and all points are used in the calculation. To validate the models a Leave One Out (LOO) cross validation approach was used. The models were assessed by comparing the measured and predicted SOC contents of the samples using the root mean squared error (RMSE), the coefficient of determination (R^2) and Ratio of performance to determination (RPD).

Results of trial fields – Plassteeg (Netherlands)

Figure 7. Scatterplot of the measured Soil Organic Carbon content (meas, %) against the predicted SOC (pred) for the Plassteeg field in the Netherlands. The predictions were validated using a Leave One Out cross-validation method.

In Fig.7, the scatter plots of these methods are given for one of the locations, using LOO. In comparing the results for this location, it appears that the differences in possible application should be taken into account as much as the statistical metrics indicating the accuracy and precision of the results. The results of the global mean calculations are one number for the entire field. This serves a different purpose than the result of the geostatistical maps that are obtained with inverse distance weighting or (ordinary) kriging. The first may be for a carbon stock (change or credit) calculation, the latter may be for improving field management for e.g. carbon or precision farming and soil health purposes.

The different spatial results obtained with the different methods are depicted in Fig. 8.

Another way to acquire the (declustered) global mean of a field is to take a composite sample. This provides the same result against lower costs (reduction in lab costs) provided the same sublocations are sampled, but does not allow multiple usage of the results, e.g. both for a global mean for carbon credits as well as spatial optimization of field management for carbon farming or other ecosystem service purposes. In both cases, the sampling design that is used and the sampling density (the number of points/hectare) will affect the results. Typically the more (sub)samples the higher the accuracy (when distributed well spatially), but also the higher the costs. The optimum for this cost/accuracy balance is application dependent. The EJP SOIL ProbeField project provides costs/accuracy information for soil sensing. For derivation of an unbiased global mean a probability sampling design is needed, for mapping this is advisable but not needed (Brus, 2022).

Figure 8. Maps of the predicted Soil Organic Carbon content (mass, %) using the different methods for the Plassteeg field in the Netherlands

For Kriging the number of locations are in many cases (far) too small to estimate a semivariogram. We are therefore highly uncertain about the actual semivariogram parameters.

For the Plassteeg field in the Netherlands figure 9 shows the lowest RMSE for Ordinary Kriging and Square Inverse Distance Weighted. This indicates that there is a spatial relationship between the values of the points. To interpret the RMSE it is helpful to know the mean and range of the SOC: In this case, the mean SOC equals 2.32 mass %, and the range 1.63 - 3.10 mass %. Another way to evaluate the

models is by using the ratio of determination to performance (RPD). As suggested by Chang et al., 2001, predictions of soil property models were considered poor for $RPD < 1.4$, moderate for $1.4 < RPD < 2$, and accurate for $RPD > 2$. So, the global mean and the Voronoi model can be considered poor and the Ordinary Kriging and IDW models can be considered moderate.

Figure 9. Coefficient of determination, Root Mean Square Error and Ration of performance to determination for the models based on sample data only, site Plassteeg, the Netherlands

Results of trial fields – other European fields

For other European fields the models with the methods global mean, IDW and Voronoi polygons were also generated (Fig. 10). According to the RPD-value only, the Strickhof model based on Voronoi polygons can be considered accurate (Chang et al., 2001). At the other sites the models can be considered poor or in 3 cases moderate.

Figure 10. Mean (mass %), Root Mean Square Error (mass %) and Ratio of Performance to Deviation (no unit) for the models based on sample data for the fields.

3.2 Spectral baselines

With spectral baseline in this study, the estimation of a soil property using the bare soil reflectance values or spectra of temporally mosaicked Sentinel 2 imagery (same period as described for WP3 ie 2019-2022) is meant as described in chapter 2 and 3. This baseline was calculated for most but not all fields. The results are included in the overview table in §3.4.

3.3 DSM using measured covariates

DSM on local scale - Results of trial fields – Plassteeg (Netherlands)

The rationale for the DSM approach for local scale consisted of, first estimating semi-variogram, then in case of nugget perform multiple linear regression; if the variogram could be fitted, then kriging was carried out, either regression kriging or kriging with one or more external drifts. In DSM, the spatial correlation of soil properties with the soil forming factors is used, as explained in chapter 2. In this study the different bands of Sentinel 2 imagery (Red, Green, Blue, NIR, several Red Edge bands, SWIR) and the Copernicus DEM are used, as are any available proximal soil sensing data. Not all fields have this data available (**Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**). To understand the dependencies between the available ancillary layers, a correlation matrix has been generated, for instance in the Dutch site Plassteeg in Fig. 11. This example shows that several Sentinel and proximal data layers are strongly correlated ($R^2 = 0.95$).

When building the models, the 10 layers that show the highest correlations with the measured SOC are used. This prevents the building of models with too few levels of freedom (overfitting a model). These 10 best performing layers are subsequently used to build linear models (lm) and Partial Least Square models (pls). The pls models are not presented here because these models are as good as the lm models but are less easy to explain and less intuitive. We have therefore chosen to only present the lm models. We used Akaike's information criterium to select the optimal model. This method helps to select a model with not too many baselines but also a good fit.

Other methods, such as regression kriging or random forest require a reasonably large number of points to reliably estimate a semi-variogram or build the trees, e.g. 100 or 150 and more. These methods are therefore not applied in this study on fields with less than 100 points.

Plassteeg
SOC, depth 0-30 cm

Figure 11. Correlation matrix for Plassteeg field (Netherlands) of the SOC with the available baselines (S2: Sentinel-2, Sat21: Satellite 2021, Sat20: Satellite 2020, MS: drone Multispectral, EMI: Electromagnetic Induction (proximal), ga: Gammasspectrometer (proximal), EC: Electroconductivity (proximal), dp: dipool (proximal), ahn: Dutch elevation model based on LiDAR)

In Figs. 12 and 13, the results of the analysis for the Dutch Plassteeg field are depicted. For this field, a high resolution DEM and several proximal soil sensing layers are available, including a multispectral UAV image. The model based on Gamma or Multispectral data shows a negative R^2 . This indicates that the mean as prediction model performs better.

The model with the smallest RMSE and a high RPD is based on a combination of Gamma and EMI proximal data. The RPD indicates that only these models can be considered as moderate, and the other models as poor. The gamma baselines were only available for the southern part of the site, resulting

in only half of the measurements that could be used for the model calibration and evaluation. Therefore, the RMSE and R^2 could not be compared to the RMSE and R^2 of the other models.

Besides these gamma-based models, the model with a low RMSE and a relatively high R^2 is the model with a combination of Satellite, multispectral UAV and Proximal data layers, although it is questionable if the multispectral UAV data contributed much, given their low performance. The RMSE (0.26) is about equal to the RMSE of the IDW-model (0.27). So, potentially, additional data layers can help to get a more accurate map of the SOC. The R^2 's of all models are low (< 0.5). The proximal data layers perform a bit better than the satellite data layers, which outperform the multispectral UAV data by far in this study. The low R^2 's are probably due to the limited variation in SOC on the field, the timing of the data acquisition and the differences in original resolution. We did not investigate the effect of sample amount and density to the results. The selected (eight!) data layers are: ec3, ec5, ec8, ec10, Sat20_I, Sat20_G, S2_R2, S2_R3.

The Random Forest model with all data layers as input is used to select the 5 most promising data layers. This results in an equally good model (RMSE and RPD) compared to the linear regression model.

Figure 12. Coefficient of determination, Root Mean Square Error and Ratio of Performance to Deviation for the models based on baselines data, site Plassteeg, the Netherlands

Figure 13. Scatterplots for the linear models of the measured Soil Organic Carbon content (meas, %) against the predicted SOC (pred). The predictions were validated using a Leave One Out method.

DSM on regional scale

Satellite-based soil organic carbon content (SOC) mapping over wide regions is generally hampered by the low soil sampling density and the variation in soil sampling collection dates. Some unfavourable topsoil conditions, such as high moisture, roughness, the presence of crop residues, the limited amplitude of SOC values and the limited area of bare soil when a single image is used, are also among the influencing factors. For two contrasted wide agricultural areas in boreal and temperate zones, Västra-Skaraborg (Sweden) and La Beauce (France), approaches relying on Sentinel-2 (S2) temporal mosaics of bare soil over ≥ 5 years jointly with Sentinel 1, SOC measurements data and other environmental covariates derived from digital elevation models and/or lithology maps and/or airborne gamma-ray data were carried out (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2023; Urbina-Salazar, 2023; Urbina-Salazar et al., 2024).

Temporal mosaicking used the approach described in §2.3. For la Beauce, covering 4838 km² in central mainland France, a variant of this approach consisted of: firstly, incorporating the soil moisture products from the Théia land data center of the French Space Agency (CNES), in order to remove the images having an average soil moisture higher than 20%; secondly, comparing seasonal periods to the whole year (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2023). For both “Plain” (923 km²) and “Till” (929 km²) subareas of Västra-Skaraborg, the temporal mosaics were all done for the Spring period but based on the 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 and 0.90 quantiles (Fig. 14).

Figure 14. Flowchart of the temporal mosaicking of bare soil in La Beauce, France (left) and Västra-Skaraborg, Sweden (right) (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2024)

Figure 15. Flowchart of the modelling approach for SOC (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2024)

Prediction models relied on quartile random forest (QRF), with 10 fold cross-validation, according to several datasets (Fig. 15): i) “Sentinel-2”, the S2 bands of a given temporal mosaic of bare soil; ii) “terrain”, the terrain covariates (Digital Elevation Model and its derivatives, plus oblique geographic coordinates); iii), “Sentinel-2” plus “terrain”; iv) “all”, i.e. “Sentinel-2”, “terrain” and a selection of relevant Sentinel-2 spectral indices.

Lessons from La Beauce (Urbina-Salazar, 2023; Urbina-Salazar et al., 2023) deal with (i) the dates and periods that are preferable to construct temporal mosaics of bare soils while accounting for soil moisture and soil management; (ii) which set of covariates is more relevant to explain the SOC variability. The models using all the covariates had the best model performance. Airborne gamma-ray thorium, slope and S2 bands (e.g., bands 6, 7, 8, 8a) and indices (e.g., calcareous sedimentary rocks, “calcl”) from the “late winter–spring” time series were the most important covariates in this model (Fig. 17).

Figure 16. Relative importance of the environmental covariates for the best SOC prediction model for La Beauce (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2023). Red squares indicate satellite remote sensing covariates, whereas purple squares designate all others.

Our results also indicated the important role of neighbouring topographic distances and oblique geographic coordinates between remote sensing data and parent material. These data contributed not only to optimizing SOC mapping performance but also provided information related to long-range gradients of SOC spatial variability, which makes sense from a pedological point of view.

These results are part of the doctoral thesis of Diego Urbina-Salazar, which was defended on May 15, 2023 (Urbina-Salazar, 2023).

Lessons from the Västra-Skaraborg deal with the impact of percentile thresholding for temporal mosaicking of bare soils in relationship with soil moisture and cloud frequency. Performance decreased from R90 to R25. Models were poorly predictive over both Plain ($RPIQ \leq 1.3$) or Till, yet with a slight improvement for Till (best $RPIQ$ 1.4). Results suggest the differences in performances according to soilscape and agricultural system, and the complex interactions due to soil moisture in satellite-based soil property mapping. This dataset is still under study in the framework of the post-doc research of M. Abubakar at EcoSys unit, INRAE.

This DSM approach through QRF provided the map of uncertainty, exemplified for la Beauce (Fig. 17).

Figure 17. SOC map (left) and uncertainty map (right) for La Beauce best model (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2023)

The map of SOC clearly exhibits some gradients in SOC distribution (Fig. 17). These gradients depict some general trends that could be linked to relationships between clay and SOC content. The uncertainty map displays large 90% prediction intervals which are rather common for DSM SOC prediction at such resolution and over a rather wide area (Lemercier et al., 2022). It is quite likely that the uncertainty could be traced to the underestimation of the extreme values for clayey soils.

3.4 Comparison with existing SOC maps

This study aims to investigate the usefulness, in terms of type of result, accuracy, precision, of several baselines, or calculation methods for soil property estimates at field scale. Based only on soil sample data or also on satellite and proximal soil sensing data layers. Combined with research on the costs and accuracies of these methods, incl factors as sampling density compared to soil property variation, this can provide practically useful insights into which methods and data sources to choose for which application of soil information. But another option isto use open, available soil (property) maps, either on national or European scale as these are usable free of charge. To understand their applicability at field scale the SOC concentrations of three often used SOC maps are compared with the measured data. This gives insight into the strengths and weaknesses of these maps. A first observation about these data is that these maps are quite coarse, the resolution varies between 300 and 750 m (for the products considered). So, this means there is about one pixel per field for the smaller fields. The scatterplots of Fig. 18 illustrate this for the Dutch Plassteeg site.

Therefore it is more suitable to compare the mean of the field with the SOC content of the available map. Comparison for the other European sites gives insight in how well the available maps can determine site specific mean SOC-contents.

Figure 18. Scatterplots of the measured SOC-content (%) on the x-axis and the SOC-content of the available SOC-maps on the y-axis for the Dutch Plassteeg field. Depicted is also the 1 on 1 line for the points with equal measured and map contents

Results of trial fields

The mean concentration based on the samples is compared with the acquired grid value of the soil map considered for each of the analysed fields in Europe (Fig. 19). For these points, the root mean square error is calculated (based on the mean value per field), shown in Table 4. It is concluded that:

- JRC LUCAS and SoilGrids perform equally bad and both grids generally overestimate the soc concentration;
- GSOC generally underestimates the measurements.

The question is whether these maps can be used to monitor the development of SOC over time. So, how often are these maps updated?

Figure 19. Scatterplot of the mean measured SOC-content (%) on the x-axis and the mean SOC-content of the available SOC-maps on the y-axis. Depicted is also the 1 on 1 line for the points with equal measured and map contents (Locations: Plassteeg, Estrup, Faardrup, Jyndeved, Silstrup, Vindum, Brogarden, Entorp, Lezirias, C_Cartagena, Grande Borne, Naizin, Altikon, Reckenholz, Strickhof, Gavere2, Udrnice, Prestavlký, Nova Ves nad Popelkou, Vezaiciai, Valinava, Lyduokiai, Osinyl, Dalaman, Kocas).

Table 4. Characteristics of the mean measured SOC-content per field (mass %) axis and the mean SOC-content based on the available maps

soc_grid	Mean Meas (mass %)	Min meas (mass %)	Max meas (mass %)	Mean grid (mass %)	Min grid (mass %)	Max grid (mass %)	RMSE (mass %)
GSOC	1.66	0.88	3.28	0.73	0.30	1.61	1.12
JRCLUCAS	1.66	0.88	3.28	3.20	1.32	7.01	2.11
SOILGRIDS (0-30cm)	1.55	0.80	3.28	3.29	1.61	7.10	2.15

Alternative from literature

Another approach for soil mapping on different scales is to pool data from regional, national and international databases to construct broadly applicable estimation models e.g. for SOC (Yuzugullu et al 2024a), but also for other soil properties such as clay content or other texture properties (Yuzugullu et al 2024b). Because of the variability and differences between sampling, analysis and even modelling approaches, such general prediction maps are often confined with large errors or relatively low prediction accuracy. It seems, that this can be overcome when the large-scale models are combined with regional (Viscarra-Rossel et al., 2024) or local (Yuzugullu et al 2024a) sampling data in a refinement process which is called spiking or support sampling.

3.5 Overview of STEROPES results for different SOC calculation methods at field scale

For the Plassteeg field the models based on samples themselves, satellite and proximal baselines are given in table 5. The IDW model which uses the samples only has an RPD =1.30 (validation by Leave One Out). This indicates that firstly, there is a spatial correlation and secondly, the samples do vary also strongly in reference to their neighbours. The question is if the satellite or proximal data can fill that gap? The model which uses all the baselines performs best (RPD =1.36). This is only a bit higher than the IDW model which uses the samples only (RPD =1.30). This small difference in performance indicates that the satellite does add extra information, but the resulting model is still considered poor regarding the RPD (Chang et al., 2001).

In table 6 the results of the models built on the sample data only, is shown According to the RPD-value only the Strickhof model based on Voronoi polygons can be considered accurate (Chang et al., 2001). At the other sites the models can be considered poor or in 3 cases moderate.

The main conclusions for WP6 are the following: 1) Most models are assessed as poor regarding the RPD (Chang et al., 2001, predictions of soil property models were considered poor for $RPD < 1.4$, moderate for $1.4 < RPD < 2$, and accurate for $RPD > 2$.)

2) There is one exception for the model with all the available data (spectral, satellite and proximal data). The proximal data seems to enhance the model.

3) Correlations between data layers are higher for aggregated data (resolution of 3 m) in comparison to the base resolution. Aggregated data is used in this report.

Table 5. Description of models with used datasets constructed in the framework of WP6

Field Year	Global mean				Voronoi polygons				IDW				Ordinary Kriging			
	Mean	RMSE	R2	RPD	Mean	RMSE	R2	RPD	Mean	RMSE	R2	RPD	Mean	RMSE	R2	RPD
Plassteeg 2021	2.32	0.36	-0.04	0.99	2.32	0.34	0.10	1.07	2.32	0.27	0.40	1.30	2.32	0.28	0.35	1.26

Field Year	DSM Satellite				DSM Proximal				DSM all			
	Mean	RMSE	R2	RPD	Mean	RMSE	R2	RPD	Mean	RMSE	R2	RPD
Plassteeg 2021	2.52	0.24	0.13	1.09	2.32	0.29	0.33	1.23	2.32	0.26	0.45	1.36

Table 6. Description of models constructed in the framework of WP6

Field and sampling year	Global mean				IDW				Voronoi polygons			
	Mean	RMSE	R2	RPD	Mean	RMSE	R2	RPD	Mean	RMSE	R2	RPD
Altikon_2022	1.60	0.16	-0.11	0.97	1.60	0.13	0.34	1.26	1.60	0.17	-0.17	0.95
Arenenberg_2022	1.59	0.16	-0.09	0.98	1.59	0.13	0.31	1.23	1.59	0.11	0.45	1.37
Brogarden_2016	2.06	1.08	-0.02	0.99	2.06	0.75	0.51	1.44	2.06	0.76	0.50	1.42
C_Cartagena_2022	0.88	0.18	-0.02	1.00	0.88	0.12	0.57	1.53	0.88	0.13	0.47	1.38
Dalaman_2021	0.80	0.19	-0.02	0.99	0.80	0.14	0.42	1.32	0.80	0.18	0.02	1.02
Entorp_2016	1.15	0.27	-0.05	0.99	1.15	0.28	-0.10	0.96	1.15	0.37	-0.99	0.72
Estrup_2012	3.22	1.67	-0.05	0.99	3.22	0.93	0.67	1.76	3.22	1.16	0.49	1.42
Faarstrup_2011	1.28	0.14	-0.02	0.99	1.28	0.11	0.31	1.21	1.28	0.13	0.04	1.03
Grande Borne_2013	1.30	0.26	-0.08	0.98	1.30	0.15	0.62	1.66	1.30	0.16	0.61	1.63
Grande Borne_2015	1.48	0.34	-0.07	0.98	1.48	0.21	0.59	1.59	1.48	0.27	0.29	1.20
Jynde vad_2012	1.82	0.21	-0.02	0.99	1.82	0.17	0.38	1.28	1.82	0.23	-0.14	0.94
Lezirias_2022	1.22	0.19	-0.04	0.99	1.22	0.14	0.43	1.34	1.22	0.15	0.34	1.24
Lezirias_2023	1.53	0.17	-0.14	0.97	1.53	0.20	-0.58	0.82	1.53	0.23	-1.12	0.71
Lyduokiai_2021	1.64	0.49	-0.02	1.00	1.64	0.42	0.26	1.17	1.64	0.54	-0.24	0.90
Naizin_2020	3.28	2.01	-0.02	0.99	3.28	1.80	0.18	1.11	3.28	2.51	-0.59	0.80
Nova Ves nad Popelkou_2021	1.41	0.42	-0.03	0.99	1.41	0.40	0.04	1.03	1.41	0.58	-1.00	0.71
Osinyl_2021	0.90	0.31	-0.07	0.98	0.90	0.34	-0.23	0.92	0.90	0.43	-1.02	0.71
Plassteeg_2021	2.32	0.36	-0.04	0.99	2.32	0.27	0.40	1.30	2.32	0.34	0.10	1.07
Reckenholz_2022	1.71	0.42	-0.10	0.98	1.71	0.33	0.30	1.23	1.71	0.32	0.36	1.28
Silstrup_2010	1.98	0.11	-0.04	0.99	1.98	0.08	0.50	1.42	1.98	0.09	0.41	1.31
Strickhof_2022	2.17	0.59	-0.09	0.98	2.17	0.36	0.60	1.61	2.17	0.25	0.81	2.32
Valinava_2021	1.54	0.21	-0.04	0.99	1.54	0.20	0.03	1.02	1.54	0.26	-0.63	0.79
Vezaiciai_2021	1.74	0.23	-0.04	0.99	1.74	0.22	0.02	1.02	1.74	0.30	-0.79	0.75
Vievinkai_2021	1.26	0.24	-0.03	0.99	1.26	0.26	-0.18	0.93	1.26	0.40	-1.71	0.61
Vindum_1992	2.03	2.81	-0.01	1.00	2.03	1.99	0.49	1.41	2.03	2.05	0.46	1.36

4. Factors influencing predictions using bare soil imagery

4.1 Soil Moisture

Short summary of results of WP 2

In WP2 we explored the potential and limits of high spatial resolution of active microwave observations, using a Sentinel-1 C-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), in combination with Sentinel 2 optical data for soil moisture (SM) prediction. A time series of S1/S2 images were used to derive remotely sensed (RS)-SM, based on the methodology developed by (El Hajj et al., 2017) at plot scale, and compare it from in-situ SM either collected from previous projects, or collected in the framework of the STEROPES project. Then soil moisture was accounted for into SOC prediction models, which confirmed that soil moisture may not only impact the prediction of SOC, but also be mitigated to some degree.

Potential and limits of Sentinel-1 C-band in combination with Sentinel 2 optical data for soil moisture (SM) prediction – results from Italy, France and Poland

In particular data coming from four main study agricultural areas in Italy, France and Poland were considered.

IT-LAZ - central Italy, Lazio region: the analysis focused on in-situ data for the period from autumn 2015 to summer 2017, covering the crop cycle of the rotation durum wheat – cover crops - processing tomato.

IT-VE - northern Italy, Veneto region : the analysis focused on the period from March 2021 to fall 2021, over a soybean irrigated field.

Naizin, France – subwatershed of 1.5 km², northwestern France, Brittany region (Zayani, 2023): the field data were collected during four field campaigns throughout the 2020-2021 agricultural year. These campaigns were scheduled during key phases of crop cycles with a maximum of bare soil and synchronized with the overpasses of the S1 and S2 satellites.

Osiny, Poland - on arable fields (3 km²) of the Agricultural Experimental Station IUNG-PIB, south-eastern Poland: the measurements of average soil moisture in the 0-30 cm layer were conducted with TDR probes in 2021-22 in 32 locations. Measurement locations were selected along transects, maximizing the variability of soil texture (from sands to loams) known from the soil map at a scale of 1:5000 and the variability of soil brightness visible on available aerial orthophotomaps.

For Italy, general conclusions of this activities are (Bazzi et. al., 2024):

- soil moisture solely predicted from S1 is underestimated during the period without rain when compared to in situ SM measured at 10 cm depth because the surface will dry much faster than the soil at this depth.
- limitation in the use of S1 for estimating soil moisture for some vegetation cover when the NDVI is high, leading to high attenuation of radar signal in C-band and to lower soil contribution.
- Good estimation of SM at 10 cm can be obtained if the SM at this depth is not substantially different from surface SM (as in the case of irrigated crops i.e., Tomato).

New measurements of SM at depth (at 5 cm), comparable with the S1 C-band penetration depth were performed in March 2023 within three agricultural fields with different crops and soils type, Rice-Loam-Sandy, Sorghum-Sandy-Loam and Maize-Silty-Cay-Loam, located in the west-central Lombardia Po Valley. At this measurement depth the estimation of RS-SM yields higher performance, also taking into account the soil texture that is, low SM content in coarse texture and higher SM content in finer texture (Fig. 20). This was corroborated by results from the French site.

Figure.20. Estimated versus observed SM. Left panel: RS SM derived from VH polarization; Right panel: RS SM derived from VV polarization

Indeed, for France, results obtained for bare soil (0-5 cm) indicate that, for surface soil moisture levels below $35 \text{ cm}^3.\text{cm}^{-3}$, there is a good agreement (Zayani et al., 2022) between the measured and the radar-derived moisture using the approach proposed by El Hajj (2017).

For Poland, using machine learning methods: Random Forest (RF) and LASSO regression, a model of soil moisture (SM) in the scale of arable fields was developed using satellite imagery (S1/S2). Both the LASSO and RF models in cross-validation (LOO) tests explained more than 60% of the variation in soil moisture. The analysis of explanatory variables importance for model errors reduction indicates that NDVI derivatives (averaged maximal and minimal NDVI values from years 2017021) are more important than dedicated soil moisture indices (like NDMI, Topographical Wetness Index) or S1 bands.

Accounting for soil moisture within SOC prediction models

Further activities developed in France and Poland addressed the accounting for soil moisture within SOC prediction models.

In France, based on the collected data in the Naizin subwatershed, the approach consisted of two stages *i*) analyzing the impact of soil moisture on predicting SOC content from S2 data by comparing two approaches: one based on selecting a single date and the other on combining multiple dates, and *ii*) evaluating the performance of Deep Neural Network (DNN) algorithms in predicting SOC content using S2 data time series combined with radar moisture data (S1-SM) and laboratory-acquired spectra. The main results obtained are:

- When using reflectance only, single-date models outperformed the combined-date models, especially those using dates featuring intermediate values of average soil moisture, specifically between 15 and $18 \text{ cm}^3.\text{cm}^{-3}$, which proved to be the most effective ($\text{RPIQ} \geq 1.7$, Zayani, 2023).
- When using time series of radar-derived moisture maps and S2 data (Fig. 21), the DNN model was the most effective compared to random forest (RF) and partial least squares (PLS) models

for predicting SOC (Zayani et al., 2023). Furthermore, adding laboratory spectral indices to these time series significantly improved the prediction performance of DNN models (Zayani et al., 2023).

- Best model was used to spatialize SOC content and the obtained map revealed correlations with soil types and topography.

Figure 21. Scatterplots of measured vs. predicted SOC content for the calibration dataset using Sentinel-2 bands and partial least squares (PLS), random forest (RF) and deep neural network (DNN) algorithms (Zayani et al., 2023).

These results are part of the doctoral thesis of Hayfa Zayani, which was defended on November 7, 2023 (Zayani, 2023).

In Poland, to assess how information about soil moisture affects the quality of predicting soil carbon content (SOC) and what is the importance of adding soil moisture information compared to soil texture, four machine learning models (in two versions: RF and LASSO) were created in which SOC was predicted based on different sets of explanatory variables. In the first model (S2bs), only the mosaic of the S2 satellite bands recorded for cloudless days with bare soil was used, in the second model (S2bs+SM) a variable was added to them, being the average soil moisture obtained from measurements carried out during the project, in the third model (S2bs+CLAY), instead of soil moisture,

a variable was added which was the measured clay fraction content, and in the fourth model (S2bs+SM+CLAY) both information on soil moisture and texture was added. Comparing the obtained cross-validation RMSE (%) errors for models presented in Fig. 22.

Figure 22. Cross-validation RMSE values (%) for spectral models of SOC content from temporal mosaics of bare soil. S2bs, S2 only; S2bs+SM, S2bs plus measured soil moisture; S2bs+CLAY, S2bs plus clay content; S2bs+SM+CLAY, S2bs plus soil moisture and clay content

It can be observed (Fig. 22) that the model predictions for SOC improve after adding soil moisture information, and even more after adding soil texture information than after adding soil moisture information; and that soil moisture information improves the model also if soil texture information is used in the model.

4.2 Soil texture

Short summary of results of WP 3

Soil consists of a heterogeneous mixture of mineral and organic particles and in most arable soils, the mineral part is by far the dominating constituent, with organic matter being often below 5%. Soil texture might influence SOC prediction performance from satellite data through clay mineral absorptions in the same spectral regions as organic matter, and by influencing soil moisture and SOC visibility (Stenberg et al., 2010; Soltani et al., 2019). The influence of soil texture on the possibility of predicting SOC using multispectral satellite data could be expected to be both favourable or unfavourable, depending on the nature of the relationship between SOC and soil texture. In the different tasks in WP3, we studied the influence of soil texture on SOC predictions at both regional and field scale at several sites in Europe reflecting different soil types and climatic conditions.

A general positive correlation between SOC and clay content is not evident in large scale data, such as e.g the European data set LUCAS, or in national data sets (Yuzugullu et al. 2024a), and it is not always the case even in local field scale datasets (Fig. 23). Instead, the correlation between SOC and clay content is site specific and varies from no correlation at all to both negative and positive correlations. This indicates that if models predicting SOC rely on a relationship between SOC and clay content, these models will not generalise well over large or different areas.

Figure 23. The relationship between SOC or SOM and clay content in a European and a national data set. And the correlation between SOC and clay content at 34 fields/farms in 10 European countries (white text indicates significant correlations).

In a study including 34 fields and neighbouring fields from 10 European countries, a significant relationship between SOC prediction performance (from site specific models) and the correlation between SOC and clay content in the soil was found. However, the relationship was weak and could only explain a small part of the overall variation in the SOC model performances across the sites. Adding information on soil texture as additional predictors to the models improved the SOC prediction on average, but the improvement varied largely between the sites. Overall, the prediction results varied largely and both predicting SOC and predicting clay was difficult. Prediction performances with $RPD > 1.5$ were observed at 8 and 12 of the 34 sites for SOC and clay, respectively (Fig. 24). Adding information on soil texture to the predictors also improved models at a slightly larger scale in Poland (3 km²) as described in §4.1. However, adding measured information on soil texture with the same resolution as the satellite data is not a practical solution, as soil texture analyses are both time consuming and expensive, reducing much of the benefits of using satellite data. Using other data related to soil texture, such as for example airborne gamma ray measurements was shown to improve SOC predictions when added to a regional satellite-based model in central France (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2023), so this might be a more cost-effective option.

The relative importance of the different satellite bands in the SOC and clay models from the study with the 34 sites, indicated that the models for the two soil properties used to some degree different information in the satellite data. The wavelength range in the red and close to the NIR region was more important for SOC predictions whereas the region around 2200 nm was more important in the clay models. However, this varied largely between the different sites and was only apparent when considering all sites in the study. Nevertheless, the observed differences are corresponding to what has been reported as important spectral regions for SOC and clay predictions (e.g. Stenberg et al., 2010; Gholizadeh et al., 2020).

Figure 24. **A)** Performance of site-specific PLSR models for predicting SOC using satellite data. **B)** Performance of site-specific PLSR models for predicting clay using satellite data. RPD and ccc were determined in leave-one-out cross-validation. Dotted lines indicate the performance of the simple baseline model, which always predicts the mean of SOC or clay in the training data (ignoring the satellite information). The solid lines are eye-guides only. (Figure from Wetterlind et al, submitted June 2024)

4.3 Dry and green vegetation

Short summary of results of WP 4

The performance of remote sensing in agricultural lands is usually hindered by dry vegetation which covers the soil surface throughout a significant part of the year. The unique spectral features of dry vegetation can be used to distinguish them from the bare soil within the acquired imagery. Dry vegetation spectra show a broad absorption band around 2100 nm which is related to some structural compounds such as lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose (Daughtry et al., 1996). Lignin also has an absorption feature at around 2300 nm which can be employed for discrimination of the crop residues from bare soil (Elvidge 1990). In addition, crop residue causes a general descending trend in the reflectance within the range of 1600 nm to 2300 nm, which is totally different from the bare soil relatively constant reflectance trend between 1600 and 2300 nm (Castaldi et al., 2019). In addition, WP4 activities included spectral measurements performed in Nouzilly, France on exogenous organic matter (EOM) applications, for the purpose of detecting them from sparsely covering green vegetation of an emerging wheat.

Exploiting spectral features of dry vegetation to fine-scale extracting of bare soil

According to these spectral differences, two main methods have been used so far to identify bare soil pixels from dry vegetation (Khosravi et al., 2024): the (i) index-based (empirical) and (ii) spectral unmixing methods. Regarding the index-based approach, statistical relationships are being

constructed using specific spectral bands, and thresholds are being defined for recognition and mapping of different types of surface cover classes. Spectral unmixing is breaking the mixed spectra of a pixel down into a set of spectral responses of the constituent materials, known as endmembers, and providing some fractional values indicating the abundances of each endmember within that pixel.

This study (Khosravi et al., 2024) was to compare the performance of the index-based and unmixing-based classification approaches as well as their integration on discrimination of the bare soil pixels on Sentinel-2 and Landsat 08-OLI single-date scenes from dry vegetation. It was carried out on four local agricultural sites in the Czech Republic. A reference soil cover RGB image representing the percentages of the cover classes in each band was created using airborne hyperspectral imagery along with same date “ground truth” photographs taken at the sampling points. A so-called “reference” bare/non-bare soil binary map was also produced after classification of the reference image pixels to bare and non-bare (Fig. 25). The bare soil fraction images obtained by applying different classification approaches on different satellite data were compared with the reference image at 400 points evenly distributed all over the area. Finally, random forest models were developed to predict SOC using sample-pixels retrieved as bare soil by each of the classification approaches.

Figure 25. Reference maps prepared after classification of the reference image for a) Nová Ves nad Popelkou, b) Jičín, c) Klučov and d) Přestavlky sites (Khosravi et al., 2024)

According to the results (Fig. 26), the best bare soil fractions estimations were obtained when using the integrated approach combining spectral indices thresholding and spectral unmixing for bare soil detection. Furthermore, bare/non-bare soil binary maps produced by this approach were more accurate than the others. SOC prediction models performed best on outputs of the integrated approach, while the highest average prediction errors were yielded by the index-based approach. In conclusion, classification of soil cover using the integrated approach led to more slightly accurate extraction of bare soil and higher performance SOC prediction models, on both types of satellite data.

Figure 26. Scatter diagrams comparing the observed and estimated bare soil fractions from Landsat8 (a, b, c) and Sentinel-2 (d,e, f) using a, d) Index-based, b, e) unmixing-based, and c, f) integrated approaches (at 400 selected pixels distributed evenly throughout the whole study area) (Khosravi et al., 2024)

Detecting exogenous organic matters (EOMs) from sparsely covering green vegetation

Spectral measurements were performed in Nouzilly, France on exogenous organic matter (EOM) applications in Spring 2022. The analysis of the spectra showed the utility of specific so-called EOMI indices developed on bare soil (Dodin et al., 2021) and/or the same indices divided by EVI for identifying amendment applications on emerging vegetation (Dodin et al., 2023). Relying on Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier and various combinations of covariates from Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1 data, applications of both composted manure and liquid digestate were further mapped over three periods and years in agricultural fields on a farm scale (Dodin et al., 2024). Classification performance was higher for pre- and post-application image pairs compared to post-application images alone and slightly improved when adding Sentinel-1 data. The areal percentage of the highest uncertainty class covered less of 10% of the mapped area regardless of the year, underscoring the potential of Sentinel-2 and 1 for monitoring EOM applications.

These results are part of the doctoral thesis of Maxence Dodin, which was defended on November 10, 2023 (Dodin, 2023).

4.4 Salinity

Short summary of results of WP 5

Two master internships that were co-supervised, in collaboration with the Ecole Supérieure d'Agriculture de Mograne (Tunisia), by Institut Agro Rennes Angers and INRAE were defended at the INAT, Tunis in late July 2023 (Bounaaja, 2023; Tebibi, 2023). They enabled to both gather the Tunisian data and provide a first insight on the proportion of saline samples, in addition to the feasibility of spectral-based predictions from Sentinel-2. The dataset was acquired on the Sminja plain, covering an area of 342 km² and located in the north-east of Tunisia at altitudes ranging from 130 m to 1290 m (Fig. 27 left). The Sminja plain has a wide variety of soil types: calcaric Cambisols, Calcisols, Vertisols,

Arenosols and Fluvisols are the most common. A total of 207 composite samples were collected from bare soil in the topsoil layer (0-20 cm). The SOC content of soil samples varies from 0.3% to 3.9%, while their salinity, expressed with electrical conductivity of saturated paste extract (ECe), ranges from 0.7 to 29.1 dS/m. However, only 17 samples have an ECe higher than 4 dS/m indicating saline soils and no correlation was observed between SOC content and soil salinity.

In Portugal, the sampling was carried out in Lezíria Grande de Vila Franca de Xira, an estuarine area of alluvial origin, covering 145 km² approximately 10 km northeast of Lisbon (Fig. 27 right). Four locations were selected for their known variability in salinity, and a total of 63 samples were collected over a subarea of ~13.4 km² to assess the impact of soil salinity levels on the potential prediction of SOC. Laboratory analysis of SOC showed very small variability, ranging from 0.87% to 1.80%, with ECe ranging from 1.16 to 10.42 dS/m, and only 15 sample locations exhibiting salinity. A detailed investigation of the correlation between bare soil imagery and SOC in this region indicated a relatively good correlation between the Bare Soil Index and SOC, with an R² of 0.49 (Farzadian et al., 2024). However, no clear impact of soil salinity on the prediction ability of SOC was observed.

While much higher soil salinity levels have been observed in previous studies of this area, exceeding 32 dS/m at deeper layers due to the presence of saline groundwater, the salinity levels in the topsoil, where the samples were taken for this project, were comparatively lower. One hypothesis from the dataset from Portugal is that the higher range of soil salinity is difficult to encounter in agricultural lands, suggesting that soil salinity within a range where crops can grow and remain viable may not significantly impact the SOC prediction from bare soil imagery. Nevertheless, the SOC range in this study area was also small to be predicted from the bare soil imagery.

Figure 27. Sampling locations over the Sminja Plain (left) and the Lezirias estuarine area, Portugal (right)

Figure 28. Sampling locations over the Campo de Cartagena site, Spain

In Spain, the field campaigns aimed at collecting saline soils were carried out over Campo de Cartagena in July 2021 (Fig. 28). A total of 122 samples were collected over an area of 12.6 km² to assess the impact of soil salinity levels on the potential prediction of SOC. Laboratory analysis of SOC showed even smaller variability compared to Lezíria, ranging from 0.44% to 1.80%, and E_c ranging from 0.14 to 2.06 dS/m that is no salinity according to standards. The collected dataset served for WP3 and WP6.

Table 7. Description of soil datasets constructed in the framework of WP5

<u>Study zone</u>	<u>Area (km²)</u>	<u>Dataset collected</u>	<u>Number of samples/fields</u>	<u>Sampling depth</u>	<u>Measured properties</u>
<u>Lezíria, Tagus estuary, Portugal</u>	<u>13.4</u>	<u>October 2022 and March 2023</u>	<u>63/4</u>	<u>0-20 cm</u>	<u>SOC, E_c, GWC, pH, particle size distribution</u>
<u>Campo de Cartagena, Spain</u>	<u>12.6</u>	<u>Summer 2021</u>	<u>141 / 32</u>	<u>0-20 cm</u>	<u>SOC, E_c, residual WC, pH, particle size distribution,</u>
<u>Sminja Plain, Tunisia</u>	<u>342</u>	<u>Fall 2017</u>	<u>215 / NA-</u>	<u>0-30 cm</u>	<u>SOC, E_c, CaCO₃, TOC, c(Na⁺), c(K⁺), c(Mg²⁺)</u>

Despite the great effort dedicated during the project for the sampling surveys targeting areas with potentially saline soils, as well as for gathering data in collaboration with external partners, it proved to be difficult to obtain samples with desirable soil salinity range in agricultural lands. In addition, the level of SOC and its variations was too small in study areas which made it even more challenging to assess the impact of soil salinity on SOC prediction. Because of insufficient number of regional/local datasets including sufficient number of saline soil samples, the data do not meet the standards required to support a scientific paper in a peer-reviewed journal at this stage and more data is still required for further investigation. A follow up of the work initiated in WP5 is henceforth made possible in the framework of the MELICERTES project (funded 2022-2027, coord. E. Vaudour, INRAE). Permission has been obtained for the use of the Tunisian dataset that started to be processed at INRAE (dataset owned by Tunisian entities) in the framework of a 18 months-post-doc position started in April 2024 (M. Abubakar).

5. Sentinel-2 as a basis for soil sampling strategy

Short summary of results of WP 7 (tasks and deliverables 7.1 and 7.3)

The activities carried out in the framework of the extended WP7 dealt with Sentinel-2-based soil sampling strategies (Vanderhasselt et al., 2024). The main aim was to study the possibility to rely on Sentinel-2 information as a basis for sampling strategy, comparing the satellite-based approach to a pre-existing SOC map in the region of Flanders. The satellite-based sampling strategies were developed and assessed at three test sites: one in the Pô valley (Province of Parma, Italy) and two in the province of Vlaams-Brabant (Flanders, Belgium) in the municipalities of Asse and Meise.

The satellite-based Sentinel-2 strategy using the Kennard-Stone selection algorithm was compared : i) in the Italian site, at field scale, to a simple random sampling strategy ; ii) at both Belgian sites, at farm scale, to a sampling strategy based on a pre-existing SOC map (so-called map-based).

At field-scale, while leading to an enlarged SOC content range for sample sizes higher than 35 (about 4 soil samples per hectare), the satellite-based strategy was more efficient for detecting the lowest SOC values. For a sampling size of 42 (about 5 samples per hectare), the satellite-based approach caught a much higher SOC content variability than random sampling strategy. The differences between the two sampling approaches could be attributable to the wider variability in B12 values detected by the satellite-based approach, especially for larger sampling size. This SWIR band is indeed the one most correlated with SOC values. Therefore, the satellite-based approach proved to be adequate for planning an accurate soil sampling campaign at field-scale that covers all the SOC variability, without a priori information. In comparison to random selection, the satellite-based approach seems more efficient for a sampling density higher than 4 samples per hectare.

At farm-scale, from a spectral point of view, the satellite-based approach selected, without a priori information about the SOC distribution, the same spectral variability as the map-based approach. This map-based approach did manage to select a markedly higher, although still insignificant, portion of the SOC spatial variability than the satellite-based approach. However, this difference was presumably caused by the extended buffer zone of 20 m for satellite-based compared to 10 m for map-based, which probably excluded much of the right side of the farm-scale SOC distribution. While the map-based sampling strategy proved to be effective at covering the entire range of farm-scale SOC content, even at low sampling sizes, it was less effective at limiting the variability within the SOC classes (i.e. strata). To make this approach more viable for carbon farming or monitoring initiatives the utilized SOC map would have to be substantially improved to better consider differences in environmental factors, like soil type and soil moisture content or drainage class.

A second aim was to analyse whether the satellite-based sampling could increase the accuracy of the existing SOC regional map at field-scale by performing a local (i.e. farm-scale) calibration. The satellite-based local calibration proved indeed successful in increasing the accuracy and quality of existing regional map. However, the map-based sampling strategy proved to be a slightly better approach than the satellite-based to compile the farm-scale calibration dataset for this purpose. Even at small sample sizes of around 10, we observed noteworthy improvements. Nevertheless, these improvements still fell short of most thresholds for applicability in carbon farming or monitoring initiatives.

6. Conclusion and recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

- **Challenging to estimate SOC using only Sentinel-2 satellite data.**
The results from the various WPs show variable results, with everything from good models to very poor models for SOC content, and the accuracy and precision varied from poorly to highly predictive models (RPIQ values from poor <1 to good ≥ 1.7). This was evident both for field or farm scale models, and regional scale models. Estimating SOC from Sentinel-2 satellite data appears challenging and even difficult, especially for places where spectral models are poor, in which it is mandatory to account for disturbing factors.
- **Benefits with using times series**
For all studied areas, the benefit of considering time series appeared obvious in order to consider the largest sample with bare soil, on a local scale (Castaldi et al., 2023; Zayani et al., 2023; Wetterlind et al., 2024; WP6 results) as well as on a regional scale (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2021, 2023; Urbina-Salazar, 2023). For many sites in this project, even though thorough soil sampling was carried out, single date images did not enable to have a sufficient number of such samples. However, using time series is still challenging in order to retrieve the best suitable quantile of reflectance and the best period to consider.
- **Influence of soil moisture**
Results obtained in Italy help to better characterize the soil condition suitable for Sentinel-1 - derived soil moisture estimation (Bazzi et al., 2024), which was confirmed for the French Brittany site (Zayani, 2023). Accounting for soil moisture within SOC modelling approach led to improved SOC predictions, particularly through a deep learning framework (Zayani et al., 2023), or within a DSM framework on regional scale (Urbina-Salazar et al., 2023).
- **Influence of soil texture**
Correlations between SOC and clay content (both positive and negative) can help prediction performance for SOC from satellite data. However, the relationship found was weak and could only explain a small part of the overall variation in the SOC model performances across sites (Wetterlind et al., 2024).
- Adding information on soil texture as additional predictors to the models improved the SOC prediction on average, but the improvement varied largely between the sites (Wetterlind et al., 2024).
- **Influence of dry and green vegetation**

Hyperspectral airborne data can be used to derive detailed map of dry and green vegetation through spectral unmixing, hence a more precise map of bare soil extent (Khosravi et al., 2024).

Results from the French Nouzilly experiment provided useful spectral indices to detect dry vegetation in the form of organic green compost, in addition to discriminate organic amendments spread on emerging crop (Dodin et al., 2021, 2023). It was possible to map them from bidate pairs (Dodin et al., 2024).

- ***Influence of salinity.***

WP5 initially aimed to assess the capability of Sentinel-2 data to predict SOC contents in the context of salinity; it was possible to derive SOC contents in the two sites of Tunisia and Portugal that had soil salinity from the very topsoil, but given the limited number of such samples, the specific influence of soil salinity could not be assessed.

- ***Base line study in WP6***

On both local and regional scales, incorporating gamma-ray and/or Sentinel-2 data leads to improve the prediction models compared to the baselines. On a local scale, from the results of the Plassteeg site, the proximal data seem to outperform both gamma and Sentinel-2. In all cases, the more data, the better.

- ***Hyperspectral data in WP7***

The EnMap data seem promising compared to Sentinel-2 , according to the results obtained from two sites in the Czech Republic.

- ***Sampling strategy in WP7***

For the purpose of sampling strategy, our results suggest that Sentinel-2 data may be used as a basis for soil SOC sampling, compared to a regional SOC map; but may not fulfil the purpose of local calibration for an existing map.

6.2 Recommendations

- The results may not support SOC mapping and monitoring for detection of the small changes in SOC that is needed in for example in carbon farming, using Sentinel-2 data. However, the precision and representation of spatial patterns might still be good enough to support soil and crop management.
- The use of temporal mosaics from time series may increase the area with good bare soil conditions and leads to more stable reflectance values on individual fields.
- Adding information on soil moisture is a plus.
- Combining information from satellite data with soil texture and/or information related to soil texture (e.g. airborne gamma ray measurements) can improve SOC prediction results.
- Depending on the aim of soil data acquisition, the type of result and required precision and accuracy can guide the analysis methods and added value of Sentinel 2 imagery.

6.3 Knowledge gaps

- There are still many factors influencing SOC prediction performance using satellite data that were not considered in the present study and that need further investigation, especially soil roughness.
- Part of this research was not carried out in all project geographies. Extension to these geographies will inform on the general applicability of the results.
- The effect of scale and generalisation of models still needs more insight over time and space.
- The cost-effectiveness of the methodologies applied in this research has not been analysed and should consider main potential applications of satellite based soil information.
- ...

6.4 Suitability for various purposes of EO for soil estimates for different uses

We expect a number of relevant outcomes: first, a step-forward for digital soil mapping (DSM) of SOC content, a step-forward for the remote sensing of soils; second, enhancement of transnational collaboration and impact on approaches for carbon balance accounting; and finally, opening up of links with stakeholders for an enhanced use of remote sensing.

The results from this project on possibilities and limitations of using remote sensing for estimations of soil organic carbon can act as guides for when and how remote sensing can be used and with what precision - *National / Regional Policymakers, Extension Officers*

The resulting accuracies for estimation of soil properties can be used to guide soil data acquisition choices for monitoring, policy development, facilitation of satellite soil services, possibly aid soil sampling location selection, land management - *National / Regional Policymakers, Extension Officers*.

The VegRV Software developed in this project presents an opportunity to accurately evaluate the status of vegetation on the ground, which could potentially improve the prediction accuracy of SOC using remote sensing data. – *Researchers, industry (tool developers)*

Spatial pattern estimation and use of bare soil satellite and other ancillary data for digital soil mapping is key data for field to regional scale applications, e.g. for land use planning, agricultural land management, soil health management choices, etc.

Using bare soil reflectance for prediction of SOC content using satellite imagery at field or smaller regional scales might not be accurate enough for benchmarking SOC content and calculating SOC change in smaller ranges (e.g. $\leq 3 \text{ g.k}^{-1}$).

List of references

- Arrouays, D., Lagacherie, P., Hartemink, A.E., 2017. Digital soil mapping across the globe. *Geoderma Regional* 9, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2017.03.002>
- Bazzi, H., Baghdadi, N., Nino, P., Napoli, R., Najem, S.; Zribi, M., Vaudour, E. *Water* **2024**, 16, 40. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16010040>
- Bounaaja S., 2023. Evaluation de l'effet de la salinité sur la teneur en carbone organique des sols dans la plaine de Sminja (NE de la Tunisie) à partir des données multispectrales Sentinel-2. Mémoire de master 2 «géomatique appliquée à l'agriculture et à l'environnement », INAT Tunis. Internship defended on 21th July 2023 cosupervised by H. Aïchi, Y. Fouad, D. Michot, and E. Vaudour.
- de Brogniez, D., Ballabio, C., Stevens, A., Jones, R.J.A., Montanarella, L. and van Wesemael, B. (2015), A map of the topsoil organic carbon content of Europe generated by a generalized additive model. *Eur J Soil Sci*, 66: 121-134. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12193>
- Brus, D.J. 2022. *Spatial Sampling with R* (1st ed.). Chapman and Hall/CRC. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003258940>
- Cao, Y., Bao, N., Liu, S., Zhao, W., Li, S., 2020. Reducing moisture effects on soil organic carbon content prediction in visible and near-infrared spectra with an external parameter orthogonalization algorithm. *Can. J. Soil. Sci.* 100, 253–262. <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjss-2020-0009>
- Castaldi, F., Chabrillat, S., Don, A. and van Wesemael, B., 2019. Soil organic carbon mapping using LUCAS topsoil database and Sentinel-2 data: An approach to reduce soil moisture and crop residue effects. *Remote Sensing*, 11(18), p.2121.
- Castaldi, F., 2021. Sentinel 2 and Landsat 8 Multi Temporal Series to Estimate Topsoil Properties on Croplands.
- Castaldi, F., Hueni, A., Chabrillat, S., Ward, K., Buttafuoco, G., Bomans, B., Vreys, K., Brell, M., Van Wesemael, B., 2019. Evaluating the capability of the Sentinel 2 data for soil organic carbon prediction in croplands. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 147, 267–282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2018.11.026>
- Chang, C.W., Laird, D.A., Mausbach, M.J. and Hurburgh, C.R., 2001. Near-infrared reflectance spectroscopy–principal components regression analyses of soil properties. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 65(2), pp.480-490.
- Chen, S., Arrouays, D., Leatitia Mulder, V., Poggio, L., Minasny, B., Roudier, P., Libohova, Z., Lagacherie, P., Shi, Z., Hannam, J., Meersmans, J., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Walter, C., 2022. Digital mapping of GlobalSoilMap soil properties at a broad scale: A review. *Geoderma* 409, 115567. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2021.115567>
- Daughtry, C.S.T., McMurtrey, J.E. Chappelle, E.W., Hunter, W.J. and Steiner, J.L., 1996. Measuring crop residue cover using remote sensing techniques. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 54, pp.17-26.
- Dodin M., 2023. Télédétection des épandages de produits résiduels organiques : contribution des séries Sentinel-2 et 1. Thèse de Doctorat en Sciences du sol. AgroParisTech, Université Paris-Saclay, UMR INRAE EcoSys. <https://www.theses.fr/2023UPASB064>
- Dodin, M., Levavasseur, F., Savoie, A., Martin, L., Foulon, J., Vaudour, E., 2023. Sentinel-2 satellite images for monitoring cattle slurry and digestate spreading on emerging wheat crop: a field

spectroscopy experiment. Geocarto International 38, 2245371.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10106049.2023.2245371>

Dodin, M., Levavasseur, F., Savoie, A., Martin, L., Vaudour, E., 2024. Mapping compost and digestate spreadings from Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1 on a farm scale. Annual Science Days 2024, EJP-SOIL, Jun 2024, Vilnius (Lituanie), Lithuania. Oral presentation <https://ejpsoil.eu/annual-science-days-2024>. (hal-04654536)

Dodin, M., Smith, H.D., Levavasseur, F., Hadjar, D., Houot, S., Vaudour, E., 2021. Potential of Sentinel-2 Satellite Images for Monitoring Green Waste Compost and Manure Amendments in Temperate Cropland. Remote Sensing 13, 1616. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13091616>

El Hajj, M., Baghdadi, N., Zribi, M., Bazzi, H. Synergic Use of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 Images for Operational Soil Moisture Mapping at High Spatial Resolution over Agricultural Areas. Remote Sens. 2017, 9, 1292.

Elvidge, C.D., 1990. Visible and near infrared reflectance characteristics of dry plant materials. Remote Sensing, 11(10), pp.1775-1795.

Farzaman, M., Paz A.M., Castanheira N. L., Gonçalves M. C., 2024. Advancements in non-invasive soil salinity monitoring: integrating electromagnetic induction, inversion, and remote sensing techniques. Annual Science Days 2024, EJP-SOIL, Jun 2024, Vilnius (Lituanie), Lithuania. Oral presentation <https://ejpsoil.eu/annual-science-days-2024>.

Gholizadeh, A., Saberioon, M., Viscarra Rossel, R.A., Boruvka, L., Klement, A. 2020. Spectroscopic measurements and imaging of soil colour for field scale estimation of soil organic carbon, Geoderma, 357, 113972. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2019.113972>.

Gomez, C., Vaudour, E., Richer-De-Forges, A.C., 2024. Remote sensing of soils: a tool for digital soil mapping. Challenges and limitations. *EJP SOIL Webinars*, EJP Soil, Feb 2024, Webinaire, France. 56p. (hal-04438779)

Grunwald, S., 2010. Current State of Digital Soil Mapping and What Is Next, in: Boettinger, J.L., Howell, D.W., Moore, A.C., Hartemink, A.E., Kienast-Brown, S. (Eds.), Digital Soil Mapping. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, pp. 3–12. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-8863-5_1

Grunwald, S., Vasques, G.M., Rivero, R.G., 2015. Chapter One - Fusion of Soil and Remote Sensing Data to Model Soil Properties, in: Sparks, D.L. (Ed.), Advances in Agronomy. Academic Press, pp. 1–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.agron.2014.12.004>

Kennard, R.W., Stone, L.A., 1969. Computer Aided Design of Experiments. Technometrics 11, 137. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1266770>

Khosravi, V., Gholizadeh, A., Castaldi, F., Saberioon, M., Ageman Prince, C., Žižala, D., Kodešová, R., Borůvka, L., 2024. Semi-automatic supervised bare soil pixels retrieval: impact of different classification approaches on soil organic carbon prediction. Annual Science Days 2024, EJP-SOIL, Jun 2024, Vilnius (Lituanie), Lithuania. Oral presentation <https://ejpsoil.eu/annual-science-days-2024>

Knadel, M., Castaldi, F., Barbetti, R., Ben-Dor, E., Gholizadeh, A., Lorenzetti, R., 2022. Mathematical techniques to remove moisture effects from visible–near-infrared–shortwave-infrared soil spectra—review. Applied Spectroscopy Reviews 58, 629–662. <https://doi.org/10.1080/05704928.2022.2128365>

Lemercier, B., Lagacherie, P., Amelin, J., Sauter, J., Pichelin, P., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Arrouays, D., 2022. Multiscale evaluations of global, national and regional digital soil mapping products in France. Geoderma 425, 116052. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2022.116052>

McBratney, A.B., Mendonça Santos, M.L., Minasny, B., 2003. On digital soil mapping. *Geoderma* 117, 3–52. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061\(03\)00223-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(03)00223-4)

Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Chen, Q., Baghdadi, N., Chen, S., Gomez, C., Jacquemoud, S., Martelet, G., Mulder, V.L., Urbina-Salazar, D., Vaudour, E., Weiss, M., Wigneron, J.-P., Arrouays, D., 2023. Remote Sensing Data for Digital Soil Mapping in French Research—A Review. *Remote Sensing* 15, 3070. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15123070>

Poggio, L., de Sousa, L. M., Batjes, N. H., Heuvelink, G. B. M., Kempen, B., Ribeiro, E., and Rossiter, D.: SoilGrids 2.0: producing soil information for the globe with quantified spatial uncertainty, *SOIL*, 7, 217–240, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-7-217-2021>

Prasad, A.M., Iverson, L.R., Liaw, A., 2006. Newer Classification and Regression Tree Techniques: Bagging and Random Forests for Ecological Prediction. *Ecosystems* 9, 181–199. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-005-0054-1>

Soltani, I., Fouad, Y., Michot, D., Bréger, P., Dubois, R., Cudennec, C. 2019. A near infrared index to assess effects of soil texture and organic carbon content on soil water content. *European J Soil Science* 70, 151–161. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12725>

Stenberg, B., Viscarra Rossel, R.A., Mouazen, A.M., Wetterlind, J. 2010. Chapter Five - Visible and Near Infrared Spectroscopy in Soil Science, in: Sparks, D.L. (Ed.), *Advances in Agronomy*. Academic Press, pp. 163–215. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113\(10\)07005-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113(10)07005-7)

Storch, T., Honold, H.-P., Chabrillat, S., Habermeyer, M., Tucker, P., Brell, M., Ohndorf, A., Wirth, K., Betz, M., Kuchler, M., Mühle, H., Carmona, E., Baur, S., Mücke, M., Löw, S., Schulze, D., Zimmermann, S., Lenzen, C., Wiesner, S., Aida, S., Kahle, R., Willburger, P., Hartung, S., Dietrich, D., Plesia, N., Tegler, M., Schork, K., Alonso, K., Marshall, D., Gerasch, B., Schwind, P., Pato, M., Schneider, M., De Los Reyes, R., Langheinrich, M., Wenzel, J., Bachmann, M., Holzwarth, S., Pinnel, N., Guanter, L., Segl, K., Scheffler, D., Foerster, S., Bohn, N., Bracher, A., Soppa, M.A., Gascon, F., Green, R., Kokaly, R., Moreno, J., Ong, C., Sornig, M., Wernitz, R., Bagschik, K., Reintsema, D., La Porta, L., Schickling, A., Fischer, S., 2023. The EnMAP imaging spectroscopy mission towards operations. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 294, 113632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2023.113632>

Tebibi H.E., 2023. Fusion des données multispectrales Sentinel-2 et hyperspectrales, acquises à l'aide d'un spectroradiomètre de terrain dans le domaine Vis-PIR pour la prédiction spatiale des teneurs en carbone organique du sol à l'échelle de la plaine de Sminja (NE de la Tunisie). Mémoire de master 2 «géomatique appliquée à l'agriculture et à l'environnement», INAT Tunis. Internship defended on 21th July 2023 cosupervised by H. Aïchi, Y. Fouad, D. Michot, and E. Vaudour.

Urbina Salazar D., 2023. Contribution des séries temporelles satellitaires à la cartographie du carbone organique des sols cultivés à divers échelons régionaux Thèse de Doctorat, Université Paris-Sud. Université Paris-Saclay.

Urbina-Salazar, D., Vaudour, E., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Chen, S., Martelet, G., Baghdadi, N., Arrouays, D. 2023. Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1 Bare Soil Temporal Mosaics of 6-year Periods for Soil Organic Carbon Content Mapping in Central France. *Remote Sensing* 15, 2410. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15092410>

Urbina-Salazar, D., Wetterlind, J., Castaldi, F., Arrouays, D., Richer-de-Forges, A., Chen, S., Martelet, G., Baghdadi, N., Vaudour, E., 2024. Temporal S2/S1 mosaics combined with environmental covariates for regional SOC mapping: lessons from la Beauce (France) and the Västra-Skaraborg (Sweden). Annual Science Days 2024, EJP-SOIL, Jun 2024, Vilnius (Lituanie), Lithuania. Poster presentation <https://ejpsoil.eu/annual-science-days-2024>

Vanderhasselt, A., Castaldi, F., Saberioon, M., Callens, B., Berckvens, N., Ilias, P., Quataert, P., Ruysschaert, G., Dal Prà, A., 2024. Satellite-based (Sentinel-2) soil sampling strategies for SOC estimation at field- and farm-scale. Deliverables D7.1 - D7.3 of the STEROPES project, EJP-SOIL, 31th July 2024, 71 pages.

Vaudour, E., Gholizadeh, A., Castaldi, F., Saberioon, M., Borůvka, L., Urbina-Salazar, D., Fouad, Y., Arrouays, D., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Biney, J., Wetterlind, J., Van Wesemael, B., 2022. Satellite Imagery to Map Topsoil Organic Carbon Content over Cultivated Areas: An Overview. *Remote Sensing* 14, 2917. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14122917>

Vaudour, E., Gomez, C., Lagacherie, P., Loiseau, T., Baghdadi, N., Urbina-Salazar, D., Loubet, B., Arrouays, D., 2021. Temporal mosaicking approaches of Sentinel-2 images for extending topsoil organic carbon content mapping in croplands. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation* 96, 102277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2020.102277>

Vaudour E., Wetterlind, J., 2021. The STEROPES project aims to evaluate satellite observation for predicting topsoil carbon. *EJP SOIL Newsletter*, 15 July 2021, 2 p. <https://ejpsoil.eu/about-ejp-soil/news-events/item/artikel/evaluating-satellite-observation-for-predicting-topsoil-carbon>

Viscarra Rossel, R. A., Shen, Z., Ramirez Lopez, L., Behrens, T., Shi, Z., Wetterlind, J., Sudduth, K.A., Stenberg, B., Guerrero, C., Gholizadeh, A., Ben-Dor, E., St Luce, M., Orellano, C. 2024, An imperative for soil spectroscopic modelling is to think global but fit local with transfer learning. *Earth-Science Reviews*, Volume 254, 104797, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2024.104797>

Wadoux, A.M.J.-C., Padarian, J., Minasny, B., 2019. Multi-source data integration for soil mapping using deep learning. *SOIL* 5, 107–119. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-5-107-2019>

Wadoux, A.M.J. -C., Samuel-Rosa, A., Poggio, L., Mulder, V.L., 2020. A note on knowledge discovery and machine learning in digital soil mapping. *European J Soil Science* 71, 133–136. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12909>

Wadoux, A.M.J.-C., Heuvelink, G.B.M., De Bruin, S., Brus, D.J., 2021. Spatial cross-validation is not the right way to evaluate map accuracy. *Ecological Modelling* 457, 109692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2021.109692>

Wetterlind, J., Simmler, M., Castaldi, F., Borůvka, L., Gabriel, J.L., Gomes, L.C., Kivrak, C., Khosravi, V., Koparan, M.H., Lázaro-López, A., Łopatka, A., Liebisch, F., Rodriguez, J.A., Savaş, A.Ö., Stenberg, B., Tunçay, T., Vinci, I., Volungevičius, J., Žydelis, R., Vaudour, E. Influence of soil texture on the estimation of soil organic carbon using Sentinel-2 temporal mosaics. *Submitted to European journal of soil science in June 2024*.

Yuzugullu, O., Fajraoui, N., Don, A., Liebisch, F., 2024a Satellite-based soil organic carbon mapping on European soils using available datasets and support sampling. *Science of Remote Sensing*, Volume 9, 100118, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.srs.2024.100118>

Yuzugullu, O., Fajraoui, N. and Liebisch, F. 2024b "Soil Texture and Ph Mapping Using Remote Sensing and Support Sampling," in *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, doi: 10.1109/JSTARS.2024.3422494.

Zayani, H., Zribi, M., Baghdadi, N., Ayari, E., Kassouk, Z., Lili-Chabaane, Michot, D., Walter, C., Fouad, Y. 2022. Potential of C-Band Sentinel-1 Data for Estimating Soil Moisture and Surface Roughness in a Watershed in Western France. *IGARSS 2022 – 2022 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, 6104–6107. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS46834.2022.9883957>

Zayani, H., Fouad, Y., Michot, D., Kassouk, Z., Baghdadi, N., Vaudour, E., Lili-Chabaane, Z., Walter, C. 2023. Using Machine-Learning Algorithms to Predict Soil Organic Carbon Content from Combined Remote Sensing Imagery and Laboratory Vis-NIR Spectral Datasets. *Remote Sensing*, 15(4264), 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15174264>.

Zayani, H. 2023. Estimations spatiale et temporelle des teneurs en carbone organique des sols agricoles par proxy-détection et télédétection satellitaire : Application à deux sites d'étude en Bretagne et en Tunisie centrale. Doctoral thesis, Institut Agro Rennes Angers et Université de Carthage, Institut National d'Agronomie de Tunisie. <https://theses.hal.science/tel-04503499>

